

Deliverable Document 1.1

Update to on-site computing software and hardware architecture recommendation

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1 Executive Summary

The on-site computing, network and storage needs for the EISCAT_3D transmitting and receiving sites have been discussed and updated from the first version of this document, E3DDS Deliverable 1 “On-site computing software and hardware architecture recommendation”. The Wide Area Network connections between the sites are also presented. The main updates are related to the Wide Area Network connections between the sites and the architecture of the Second Beam former.

The long-term cost of a high-capacity optical Wide Area Network between the EISCAT_3D sites has come down to compete with more traditional networking. An option has been found that allows to deploy all the computing e-infrastructure away from the remote sites to the central site. This should be an interesting option for EISCAT_3D as operational costs can be reduced and procedures made more efficient. Also, by concentrating computing e-infrastructure in one location, this presents an opportunity to build dual-purpose computing clusters. The online data processing clusters may be re-configured as useful user analysis clusters in periods when the radar is off.

The Second Beam former is split into a two-stage process between the First Stage Receive Units (FSRUs) and the computing servers that will house the RAM Ring Buffer and perform the second stage of the narrow-angle beam forming, the Ring Buffer Beam Former (RBBF) nodes. Using this model, it is estimated that one CPU of a suitable server [1] can form, in real-time, the 10 one polarization narrow-angle beams from one wide-angle beam at 5 MHz bandwidth. Therefore 10 dual socket servers are required for each receive site and 2 for the transmitting site. There are two possible choices of input network architecture between the First Stage Receiving Units to the Ring Buffer Beam Former nodes: a switch fabric or direct connections from FSRUs to RBBF servers. Whether these connections are made of (or to) internally within a site, or over an optical WAN should make no difference to the online data processing performance.

The estimates for the file writer, that writes the summed second beam former results to files, and the prompt computing, that produces higher-level time and space-integrated data products are unchanged. The long-term cost of a high-capacity optical Wide Area Network between the EISCAT_3D sites has come down to compete with more traditional networking. The optimum configuration for the site-local buffer is still proposed to be RAID-5 Solid State Drives (SSDs) directly integrated to the RBBF nodes.

A cost estimate for local clusters and networking based on national e-infrastructure providers experience is given in Appendix A. Appendix B gives an opinion on the future outlook for hardware from national e-infrastructure providers. Appendix C gives the current wide-area networking costs provided by NORDUnet at the E3DDS Stakeholder meetings.

2 Purpose

The purpose of this document is to function as a final report for the E3DDS project and an update the Deliverable 1 [2] of this project that described and recommended the on-site computing software and hardware architectures for EISCAT_3D. These recommendations are the outcome of iterative dis-

cussions between the EISCAT_3D software engineers and scientists and national provider deployment experts. The architecture is a result of close discussions and work between the on-site computing (beam former, Level 2 data processing, Level 3 data analysis and possibly satellite screening code) developers, EISCAT scientists and the operators of the national e-infrastructures.

The target readers of this document are primarily the EISCAT_3D project management and scientists. The EISCAT_3D project management can get an indication of the actual amount of computing at the different EISCAT_3D sites. Also, another target is the providers of the national e-infrastructures where EISCAT_3D will be located. The national e-infrastructure providers can see the quantity and type of computing required for EISCAT_3D and determine whether some can be run in existing computing centres.

3 Introduction

The EISCAT Scientific Association will establish EISCAT_3D, a flexible multi-static high power radar system, that will enable comprehensive three-dimensional vector observations of the atmosphere and ionosphere above Northern Fenno-Scandinavia.

The use of new radar technology, combined with the latest advances within digital signal processing, will achieve ten times higher temporal and spatial resolution than obtained by the present EISCAT radar systems. For the first time, EISCAT will also be able to measure continuously. The flexibility of the EISCAT_3D system will enable scientists to investigate upper-atmospheric and ionospheric phenomena at both large and small scales unobtainable by the present systems.

In its first stage, the EISCAT_3D system will consist of three radar sites: one having both **T**ransmitting (**TX**) and **R**eceiving (**RX**) capabilities and two with only RX capability. The sites will be remote-controlled and located in three different countries (Finland, Norway and Sweden) and will be separated geographically by approximately 130 km. Two additional receiver sites, at distances 200-250 km from the transmit site, are planned for the full EISCAT_3D system at a later stage.

EISCAT_3D will produce data at three main levels, from raw samples to physical parameters. Table 1 summarizes the EISCAT_3D data levels.

4 WAN configurations

The EISCAT_3D sites need to be connected over a Wide-Area Network (WAN) ¹. The WAN must meet capacity and latency requirements to transmit the data produced at the EISCAT_3D sites, control updates, as well as general remote management, connectivity to the long-term data center (DC) storage and direct or indirect connectivity to the internet for users. The base requirement for EISCAT_3D operations is that the data for 5 MHz case is processed in real-time from antennas to DC storage.

¹Any network that is external to a site is considered as Wide Area Network

Level	Type	Produced by	Storage	Format
1a	Ring buffer data	1 st stage beam former	4 months	UDP stream/ HDF5
1b	Beam-formed data	2 nd stage beam former	4 months	HDF5
1c	Imaging data	2 nd stage beam former	4 months	HDF5
2	Time integrated correlated data	All sites	Archived	HDF5
3a	Physical parameters	All sites	Archived	HDF5
3b	3D-voxel parameters	Data centre	Archived	HDF5
4	Derived geophysical parameters	Users	Users	Publications etc

Table 1: Summary of the EISCAT_3D data levels.

Here, we make an assumption that a site is designated to contain the “central” computing and radar operations. A logical assumption as the transmitter is physically located at the TX site in Skibotn. The WAN connections between EISCAT_3D sites have been discussed and presented at a series of Stakeholder meetings [3] and the costs are summarized in Appendix C. There are four options to connect the EISCAT_3D sites considered.

4.1 IP Routed connections

Inter-site connectivity is provided by an EISCAT-3D “LAN” (IP-routed) ring connecting the local networks of each of the sites as shown in Figure 1. There is a connection to each National Research and Education Network (NREN) for upstream traffic and the total aggregate ring capacity is 100 Gb/s. This implies an averaged maximum data rate of 33 Gb/s simultaneous output from each site.

This WAN option requires that the first and second beam forming are performed at each site. Depending on the output rate of the prompt computing processing, this could be situated at a centralized location on the IP-routed ring.

4.2 Optical DWDM connections

The Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing [4] (DWDM), an optical technology used to increase bandwidth over existing fiber optic backbones, provides an attractive alternative for connecting the EISCAT_3D sites.

DWDM works by combining and transmitting multiple signals simultaneously at different wavelengths on the same fiber. In effect, one fiber is transformed into multiple virtual fibers. A key advantage to DWDM is that it is protocol and bit-rate independent. DWDM-based networks can transmit data in IP and other protocols and can handle bit rates between 100 Mb/s and 2.5 Gb/s.

Figure 1: EISCAT_3D sites are connected via an IP-routed ring with 100 Gb/s total capacity. All online data clusters and associated LAN e-infrastructure must be deployed on the RX sites.

Therefore, DWDM-based networks can carry different types of traffic at different speeds over an optical channel. From a Quality of Service standpoint, DWDM-based networks create a lower cost way to quickly respond to bandwidth demands and protocol changes.

4.2.1 Option 1

Here a 2×100 Gb/s DWDM optical network is used to connect the EISCAT_3D RX sites to a central location as shown in Figure 2. Considering that the requirement is to process 5 MHz online data in realtime and working backwards, from prompt computing to FSRUs, along the online data processing chain:

- The Prompt Computing output can easily be sent over the WAN to a central site.
- The 5 MHz output of the second beam former of each RX site can also be sent to a central site;
- The output data rate of the FSRUs, on RX sites in 5 MHz mode, to ring buffer memory is too large for this WAN capacity.

4.2.2 Option 2a

Here the capacity of the optical DWDM connection is sized such that the e-infrastructure for the online data processing chain from ring buffer nodes onwards is located in a central computing location

Figure 2: EISCAT_3D RX sites are connected to a central DC via 2×100 Gb/s DWDM optical connections. The prompt computing nodes may be deployed to the central site.

i.e. there is computing or storage capacity on the remote sites. The FSRUs connect to an ethernet switching fabric that subsequently connects to the optical WAN as shown in Figure 3. If the RX and central sites are to be connected with a WAN capable of carrying the FSRU to ring buffer data, then the WAN must be capable of carrying the 30 MHz operations data. In “normal” 30 MHz operations mode this implies a data rate from each RX site of ≈ 1.1 Tb/s. But, if the maximum beams at 30 MHz are produced then the capacity required is ≈ 3.6 Tb/s from each RX site to the central site. This optical WAN satisfies the requirement.

4.2.3 Option 2b

This optical DWDM WAN option, shown in Figure 4, is similar to option 2a (Section 4.2.2) in concept, except that the FSRUs are connected directly to the optical network. The ethernet-optical switches at the remote and central sites are omitted.

The long-term cost of a high-capacity optical Wide Area Network between the EISCAT_3D sites has come down to compete with more traditional networking. An option has been found that allows to deploy all the computing e-infrastructure away from the remote sites to the central site. This should be an interesting option for EISCAT_3D as operational costs can be reduced and procedures made more efficient. Also, by concentrating computing e-infrastructure in one location, this reduces latency and random IP packet delays (jitter) between nodes, and presents an opportunity to build dual-purpose computing clusters. The online data processing clusters may be re-configured as useful user analysis clusters in periods when the radar is off.

Parallel computing calculations, such as 3-D calculations from multi-static measurements, normally rely on message passing interfaces that are extremely sensitive to network latency and jitter.

Figure 3: Site connections assuming 40×100 Gb/s optical connection between central and RX sites. All RX site computing clusters may be moved to the central site.

4.3 Site computing deployment

A consideration when connecting the EISCAT.3D sites over WAN is the overall network cost compared to the savings in operational costs. Locating computing clusters at the RX site(s) will incur an increased operational cost. Although, this cost can be mitigated by use of remote cluster management software for operating system and hardware. The majority of operations on a cluster are performed remotely. Only hardware-related issues such as failures and upgrades need to be addressed with the physical presence of personnel. Typically the warranty and service contracts of computing hardware (servers) are priced per unit. Therefore the price will not be appreciably different if the computing servers are distributed over RX sites or located in one central site.

Table 2 gives a summary of the various computing e-infrastructure elements that must be deployed to the remote RX sites according to each WAN connection scenario. As can be seen in Table 2, it

WAN type	Optical	Ethernet Router	RBBF Nodes	Prompt Nodes	White Rabbit	Management Cluster
IP		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Optical 1	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Optical 2a	✓	✓			✓	
Optical 2b	✓				✓	

Table 2: The various computing e-infrastructure elements required (✓) to be located on the remote RX sites according to each WAN deployment option.

is possible to move all e-infrastructure from the RX sites to the central site, given a large enough

Figure 4: Site connections assuming 60×100 Gb/s optical connection between central and RX sites. All RX site computing clusters and associated LAN may be moved to the central site.

WAN capacity. Whether this is cost-effective remains to be seen. What can be seen is there is an option (Optical 2a) that allows to deploy all the computing e-infrastructure away from the RX sites to the central site.

This should be an interesting option for EISCAT_3D as operational costs can be reduced and procedures made more efficient. Operational costs may be reduced by virtue of not having to travel to the remote sites for hardware-related issues ². Also, by concentrating computing e-infrastructure in one location and connecting via a LAN (within server racks), this reduces latency and jitter between nodes (compared to nodes connected via a WAN), and presents an opportunity to build dual-purpose computing clusters. The online data processing clusters may be re-configured as useful user analysis clusters in periods when the radar is off. Complicated parallel computing calculations such as EISCAT_3D 3-D analysis from multi-static measurements, performed on traditional hardware, rely on interfaces such as MPI [5] that are sensitive to latency and jitter between computing nodes.

It is expected that 22 RBBF nodes are required for the RX and TX sites, see Section 5.4, and therefore a powerful cluster may be created. For the prompt computing nodes, the benchmarks are still not yet precisely measured. It is expected that ≈ 14 “commodity” servers are required per RX site which implies a ≈ 30 node cluster can be built. By using techniques such as virtualization or high performance computing batch queueing (see [6]) these online data processing clusters can be used for other tasks such as user analysis during the time that the radar is off or running on a low duty cycle.

²Remote management of clusters is standard procedure these days so operating system and even BIOS/UEFI issues can be handled remotely.

Figure 5: Schematic of the E3D receiver data-flow.

5 On-site hardware

Figure 5 gives the schematic representation of the data flow within a RX (or receiving on the TX) site from the antenna sub-array first beam former to the local site storage.

5.1 First Stage Receive Unit rates

A general description of the **F**irst **S**tage **R**eceiving **U**nit (FSRU) units can be found in [7]. Development has started and the final design was ready in February 2019. There will be one FSRU per EISCAT_3D sub-array that receives 182 analog channels from 91 antennas. After analog-to-digital conversion, signals are delayed and combined (beam formed) on the Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) to form 10 wide angle beams having two polarizations each. The FPGA also performs the time delay for the first step of the second beam former that will form the narrow angle beams as described in Section 5.4. The wide angle beam data are transferred as UDP packets from each first stage receive unit via two 25 Gb/s optical links to a cluster computer that handles ring buffers, second stage beamforming and file writing.

The FSRU (FSRU_s where $s = 1, N$) attached to each of the N site³ sub-arrays are shown at the top of Figure 5. Each FSRU outputs 10 wide-angle beams that are transmitted as UDP data packets (b_s^n) where $s = 1, N$ is the sub-array number, $n = 1, 10$ is the wide-angle beam number and

³There are $N = 109$ sub-arrays on the RX sites and $N = 119$ sub-arrays on the TX site.

Figure 6: Input network that assumes 2x25 Gb/s optical connections from each FSRU directly connected to the second beam former nodes.

$p = 1, 2$ is the polarizations of the beam. The FSRUs are either directly connected to the computing nodes that contain the RAM ring buffer, or there is a switch that directs the UDP packets to the appropriate nodes. The UDP packets are written to the ring buffer ordered by beam number and polarization with all sub-array packets as a sequence $\{b_1^1{}_a, \dots, b_N^1{}_a\}$, $\{b_1^1{}_b, \dots, b_N^1{}_b\}$, $\{b_1^2{}_a, \dots, b_N^2{}_a\}$, \dots , etc of $(N \times 10 \times 2)$ (2180 on RX sites and 2380 on TX site) wide-angle beam data packets. The UDP data packets sent from the FSRUs are buffered and then sent via the two 25 Gb/s optical links once a UDP packet has been completely written.

5.2 Input network from FSRU

The input network delivers the narrow angle beam UDP streams from the two 25 Gb/s interfaces per first stage receive unit (109 or 119 depending on site) through fiber optic links from each first stage receive unit to the server nodes that contain the RAM ring buffer. These computing nodes that comprise the RAM ring buffer are the same nodes that perform the final steps of the second level beam forming: the **R**ing **B**uffer **B**eam **F**ormer (RBBF) nodes. There is a choice between connecting the first stage receive unit links directly to the RBBF nodes as shown in Figure 6 or have a switching fabric in between, as shown in Figure 7.

5.2.1 Direct Connection

The advantages of a direct connection of the first stage receive unit links is that there is no single-point-of-failure and the loss of a single RBBF node out of “ m ” nodes will only result in a fractional loss of $1/m$ of the inputs, which results in lower resolution but still judged to be usable data for $m \geq 10$. It also puts constraints on the “ m ” RBBF nodes since each must provide $238/n$ 25 Gb/s interfaces, in addition to an internal communications fabric between the nodes and a normal interface

for exporting data products and system management. A quick market survey has put the upper limit on the number of useful 25 Gb/s interfaces per 2U server at 12 or 13.

5.2.2 Switched Connection

A switching fabric (shown in Figure 7) converts the many (two each per FSRU) 25 Gb/s connections to fewer 100 Gb/s connections (for example). This networking solution allows flexible fail-over through the ability to switch any first stage receive unit to any RBBF node, which is helpful from a reliability point of view, as we can assume that server nodes will need scheduled maintenance or will have unscheduled failures. Recovery from this situation in a fully switched network situation with at least one spare ($m+1$) RBBF node can be done in milliseconds, compared to hours (or days) if someone has to travel to a remote site. Having a unique destination IP and unique port for each first level beam is also convenient for the software solution.

Switching also means that the RBBF nodes only need one or two 100 Gb/s interface per node for the incoming data, and thus more compact servers are possible. The downside is the extra cost for switches that become a point of failure that can degrade the signal from a site.

Each socket (containing multiple cores) of the CPU on a RBBF node will process the data of one polarity (p) of a wide-angle beam (n) from each first stage receive unit (p) over the whole array. For example, the ring buffer memory of the RBBF node 1 would receive UDP packets:

$$\sum_{s=1}^N \sum_{p=1}^2 b_s^1 p$$

and CPU core 1 would process data:

$$\sum_{s=1}^N b_s^1 1$$

of beam 1 from FSRU s , polarity p . Therefore, the UDP data packets of each beam and polarity from each first stage receive unit must be correctly routed to the portion of the ring buffer situated on each RBBF node.

5.3 Ring Buffer

The ring buffer is a pool of fast-access storage (e.g. DRAM, Flash, Phase-Change memory, etc) that is integral to the RBBF nodes. The narrow-beam data packets ($b_s^n p$) from the FSRUs are written to the ring buffer memory. The ring buffer size is based on the baseline 5 MHz bandwidth operation and is sized for the time that level-1b data can be written to the storage to be processed off-line or written to the disk buffer.

The minimum ring buffer should allow 100 s of 5 MHz bandwidth data to be stored, e.g. in order to search for meteors and space debris in the raw data. An upper limit on the ring buffer capacity is to store 1200 s of 30 MHz data, which is required to cover a typical scientific rocket launch with F-region (around 250 km) apogee and calculate posterior beams along the trajectory [8]. A more detailed description of the ring buffer size calculations can be found in [2]. For the RX sites the ring buffer size ranges between $\approx 4 - 50$ TB and for the TX sites between $\approx 1 - 11$ TB.

Figure 7: Input network candidate that assumes 2x25 Gb/s optical connections from each FSRU to a layer 3 switching infrastructure. A earlier option uses a single 100 Gb/s optical connection to the switching infrastructure.

If the ring buffer is to be deployed as RAM on the RBBF nodes, the RAM sockets must all be populated evenly for the best overall data throughput on the node. Given the useful size ranges of the ring buffer and volatile RAM prices, the optimum ring buffer/cost solution will only be apparent close to the time the RBBF cluster servers are purchased.

The 30 MHz bandwidth is mainly for astronomy and plasma line search (including NEIALs⁴ with plasma lines). The system will be switched to the high 30 MHz rate when NEIALs are detected, and in this case run the FSRUs at 30 MHz for an interval up to about an hour, overwriting the ring buffer in 10 s intervals and storing those with detected NEIALs to disk for offline interferometry. The time to write level 1 (a or b) data from the ring buffer memory to the disk buffer must be considered also. Writing the level 1a data out to a spinning hard disk buffer will be at least one order of magnitude slower than receiving it from the FSRUs (depending on the storage bandwidth capacity of the site local buffer).

An option for writing level 1a data in burst mode is to use local Solid State Drives (SSDs) i.e. SSDs installed in the RBBF nodes. SSDs that can handle up to 2-3 Drive Writes Per Day cost much less than RAM, probably adding only 5-10 percent to the ring buffer costs. This means the 30 MHz data could be flushed from the ring buffer in only 2-4 times as long as it took to receive from the source and enable rapid resumption of 5 MHz operations. This is under the assumption that 30 MHz

⁴Naturally Enhanced Ion-Acoustic Lines, an asymmetry in the scatter spectrum.

burst mode with raw data dumping would not occur more than 2-3 times per day on a long term average.

5.4 Second level beam former

The E3DDS deliverable 1 [2] describes the software options for the second beam former that produces 10 narrow-angle beams from each wide angle beam ⁵. A second beam former process with correct delay and decimation values is implemented when an experiment is formed.

The current solution for the second beam former is a two stage process that makes use of the FPGAs on the FSRUs to perform the long delays needed between sub-arrays, essentially shifting the start time of each beam. The summation of the results and a small phase change *i.e.* complex multiplication can then be performed in the RBBF nodes. In Section 8.4 of [9], simulations show that the simulated maximum error using this approach can be considered to be small enough. Also

By splitting the second beam former tasks between the first stage receive unit FPGA (time delays) and RBBF nodes (summation and phase change), it is expected that one socket of an RBBF node [1] can produce the 10 narrow angle beams from each wide angle beam. Given that in 5 MHz operation: the RX sites will generate 20 wide-angle beams (10 beams with 2 polarities); the TX site will generate 4 wide-angle beams. Therefore for each RX (TX) site, 10 (2) of such servers are required to process the 5 MHz data in real-time.

Also, there is no need to perform summations of outputs between the RBBF nodes and this negates the need to employ a message passing interface [5] and a high performance network for online data processing to connect the RBBF nodes on the data downstream side.

5.5 Propositions for hardware configuration

The data throughput values in different operating modes have to be considered when deciding the Ring Buffer hardware configuration. In the Fast Saving mode (at 30 MHz) all the FSRUs are sending data packets at a rate of 52 MSPS. This data stream should be written to the ring buffer in the RAM main memory.

The latest AMD EPYC 7000 processors have memory bandwidth in order of 170 GB/s (1360 Gbit/s). If all that can be used for data throughput, it means that the nominal data from FSRUs can be saved, and thus the memory bandwidth should not be a bottleneck ⁶. In the case of AMD EPYC 7000 series there 128 lines available giving 800 Gb/s of traffic in theory. In practice, from Figure 7, the FSRUs are connected to the RBBF nodes through a network layer. Each RBBF node can accommodate two PCIe4 network cards each with two 100 Gb/s connections. The traffic to the main memory is then 200 Gb/s, which is only 1/6 of full available bandwidth.

⁵10 wide-angle beams with 2 polarities gives 200 narrow angle beams in total

⁶The next version of the AMD CPU is expected to provide PCIe Generation 4 (PCIe4) as well as even better memory bandwidth, see <https://www.servethehome.com/why-amd-epyc-rome-2p-will-have-128-160-pcie-gen4-lanes-and-a-bonus/>

Figure 8: An example of a possible hardware configuration using FPGA accelerators for second beam forming.

FPGA or GPU cards can be used as an optional accelerator for prompt computing or correlators for imaging experiments, as shown in Figure 8. Accelerator cards should be connected together using fast network or direct card to card (e.g. NVLink) connections.

5.6 On-site local disk buffer

After the narrow angle beams are summed in the ring buffer nodes, the data streams need to be ordered into files and then shipped off site to a data center for permanent storage. In order to handle short interruptions and the occasional inefficient scheduling, a local buffer of at least a few minutes and preferably a few hours is needed.

The total output of the second level beam former is $32 + 32 \text{ bits} \times 200 \text{ beams} \times 5 \text{ MHz} = 8 \text{ GB/s}$ at 5 MHz operations. As mentioned in Section 5.3 the ring buffer (or SBF) nodes can be equipped

with SSDs. For example, six 400 GB SSDs in a raid 5 configuration provide 2 TB net usable buffer space, which turns into 250 seconds or $n \times 6$ minutes of effective buffer space in the 5 MHz case, and a sixth of that for 30 MHz (30 MHz will (can)not be beam formed in real time on the available compute resources though). This would also be a fast (2–4 GB/s on each node) target for saving sections of the ring buffer, where speed of writing is important to free up that part of the ring buffer for new data.

Using Non-Volatile Memory express (NVMe) for these SSDs might add a bit of cost (list prices are 1.2 times more expensive) but indications are that in a competitive tender the difference is not so big. Also NVMe reduces CPU usage for I/O and increases total speed.

5.7 File writer and prompt computing

The file writer process will take the summed narrow-angle beam results from the second beam former and write these to data files (HDF5-based format suggested) on storage. The file writer processes either run on RBBF nodes or on separate dedicated nodes, downstream of the second beam former. Dedicated nodes can also be used for summing, decimation, data analyzing and event triggering. It is preferred that the HDF5 files will be written to the local SSD buffer on the RBBF nodes then transferred to a central location. This local storage should be fast so that exceptional events can be downloaded quickly from the RBBF nodes, so SSD disks are preferred. The requirements for the file writer processes can be specified by the operating bandwidth (5 MHz or 30 MHz) and the level of data reduction within the second beam former. For example, one narrow angle beam, having 5 MHz bandwidth and two polarizations, is a continuous data stream of 80 MB/s, which is considered very small for any modern SSD disk with write speeds up to 3000 MB/s.

The overhead in writing the data to HDF5 files will be negligible as all the experiment-related information is stored in the experiment database and can be added to the HDF5 file later. The instructions for the file size, file names and destination folders are in the experiment database written when experiment has been formed. This database also includes the necessary metadata information which will be added to the files.

5.8 Additional servers for services

Operations of the experiment and maintenance tasks for the computing requires a highly available database as well as several servers to handle orchestration, software maintenance tasks, file transfer scheduling, etc. A system to run highly available databases and virtual machines could echo the one used by the NeIC NT1, and need three physical hosts with local storage.

For maximum commonality, three more nodes with the same specification of the SBF nodes would be appropriate. As a compromise to reduce the cost, they could be ordered with significantly less RAM (200–300 GB) and only 2 or 4 network interfaces.

6 On-site software

Figure 9: A schematic view of the different software components of the second beam former.

6.1 Receiver and ring buffer process

A suggested design, as shown in Figure 9, is to run a process (the ring buffer process) for each first level wide-angle beam, that listens to a dedicated port and puts all the received data into a ring buffer in the shared memory of the server node. The process reads the data stream index number from the data packet header and updates the ring buffer database table so that received data can be associated with corresponding data stream.

Once a predefined number of data packets from all sub-arrays have been written to the ring buffer, the process triggers the second beam former process dedicated to this first level beam.

The ring buffer keeps the data so that in case post-analyzer process finds an interesting event, the corresponding data can be marked as protected and to be downloaded separately. This will be done in a database table. These ring buffer areas will not be used for new data until they are released by higher level control (i.e. after the data is downloaded to the local buffer).

6.2 Timing and control network

The subsystems of EISCAT_3D must be synchronised at an accuracy of 100 picoseconds, corresponding to acceptable geometric errors in the beamforming. For this the White Rabbit timing protocol will be used. It requires a separate 1 Gb/s control network that has to be distributed over single-mode fibre connections via certified White Rabbit switches.

The radar control system will distribute commands to the PSCUs, FSRUs and transmitter controllers. It is being built around RabbitMQ messaging (an Erlang implementation not to be confused with White Rabbit) a distributed database and programmed using high level libraries developed for Python or compiled languages like Rust where appropriate.

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Appendix A Cost estimate

A cost estimate is shown here based on the text above. The costs are based on list prices [10] and are made for comparison purposes. A tender in which sufficient ⁷ amounts of equipment is being purchased can result in a 30% reduction in list prices. Given this observation, standardizing the hardware between the sites and buying under a single tender is the strategy that will deliver the most hardware for money. We assume that the number (and therefore the price) of optical cables and connectors from the FSRUs to the input network and site-local computing (i.e. second beam former) is a constant for all options. The output network (Infiniband or other technology after the SBF nodes) is also assumed to be constant, modulo the actual number of SBF nodes. The cost for a 40-port 200 Gb/s Infiniband switch is 20 k€. Infiniband switches are available with 36, 40, or possibly 80 ports.

The network switching equipment (between the FSRUs and SBF nodes) has the following prices:

25 Gbit/s ports	100 Gbit/s ports	Price (k€)	Form
48	12	30	1U
48	6	20	1U
48	4	20	1U
0	32	30	1U
0	64	80	1U

The server costs are based on servers in the Kebnekaise cluster at HPC2N in Umeå (dual CPU, 2.6 GHz, 14 cores) and 384, 768 or 1532 GB RAM (24×16 GB, 32 GB, 64 GB respectively)⁸. This spec includes 2 TB net SSD on raid-5, enough 25 GbE ports, 100 GbE NIC as a stand-in for Infiniband. This is the same specification of server as used in the benchmarking in [11].

RAM (TB)	Price (k€)	Form
0.2	14	2U
0.4	17	2U
0.8	24	2U
1.5	40	2U

The options below, based on the RX sites requirements, correspond to the topologies shown in Figures 6 and 7. An option based on a variation of Figure 7 is also provided where the optical connections from the FSRU input network layer to SBF nodes are 100 Gb/s (Option 100 Gb/s). The option for server RAM closest to 1 TB RAM is used in each case. As can be seen in the table, the cost for each option is dominated by the number of ring buffer nodes. The main cost driver of the ring buffer nodes is the amount of RAM. For example dropping the RAM to 0.4 TB per ring buffer node gives costs of 716, 788 and 874 k€ respectively.

⁷The amount of equipment purchases that trigger discounts varies by supplier and market conditions.

⁸For performance all memory channels should have the same population

Option	Optical Connectors	Switching boxes	SBF nodes	Direct cables	Total
Fig 6	119 × 2 × 25 Gbit/s 36 k€	n/a	40* 960 k€	n/a	80U 996 k€
Fig 7	119 × 2 × 25 Gbit/s 36 k€	2 × 48-25 6-100 Gbit/s 1 × 48-25 12-100 Gbit/s 70 k€	40* 960 k€		83U 1066 k€
100 Gb/s	119 × 2 × 100 Gbit/s 72 k€	4 × 32-100 Gbit/s 120 k€	40* 960 k€	23 × 100 Gbit/s 1.8 k€	84U 1154 k€

Appendix B Future outlook

Future hardware outlook

During 2019 new CPU generations from both AMD and Intel will be launched. The AMD processors are expected to bring significant increases in the number and speed of cores, while Intel is expected to bring more modest improvements. Still, a small improvement in the AVX-512 unit could bring big overall performance benefits for our use case.

At the moment AMD has higher main memory bandwidth than Intel server processors, due to four memory channels per processor rather than Intel's three. This difference is foreseen to last at least the next year or two.

There is also likely that new CPUs will bring PCI Express Generation 4, which is a doubling of the data rate for I/O. This might make it possible to pack more 100 Gb/s network interfaces into a single card or possible to use 200 Gb/s Infiniband. The current roadmaps indicate that AMD will launch CPUs with PCIe Gen4 during 2019, and Intel in the middle of 2020.

The biggest cost for the on site computing is the RAM for the ring buffer, which is historically expensive (twice as expensive during 2018 as in 2017). The prices might be going down too.

Newer SSD technologies, either flash or phase change based, might make it possible to build a cheaper ring buffer if they are reliable enough or cheap enough to overprovision sufficiently. Using something else than RAM means moving the data many more times over I/O lanes which probably requires PCIe Gen4 as well as more CPU resources (from HPC2N benchmarks, 2 GB/s disk I/O is enough to saturate a single core, which then is not available for FIR filters).

An interesting possibility for ring buffer storage device is the phase change technology developed by Intel and Micron (Optane™). This technology has earlier been used in SATA and NVMe connected storage devices but recently Optane DIMM memory modules has also become available. Optane DIMMs are slower than normal memory modules, but they are able to keep the data permanently in memory. At least in principle, Optane DIMMs could be used in ring buffer instead of normal DIMMs. It is, however, yet unclear what kind of detailed specifications Optane DIMMs have and how competitively they will be priced. In addition, so far Optane DIMMs have been available only for Intel platforms. The use of Optane DIMMs may rule out AMD as a CPU vendor.

The price for 25 Gb/s SFP28 optics modules is likely to drop from today's levels, since this is a very new technology. Rough price parity with 10 Gb/s is expected in a year or two from now, which would cut that cost by almost an order of magnitude.

Appendix C WAN costs

The wide area network costs have been presented by NORDUnet representatives in the series of E3DDS Stakeholder meetings. The Table below gives a brief summary of the costs of the technologies and the dates they were presented. The cost includes the price of installation plus yearly fees in a

Date	Technology	Cost
2018/09/17	100 Gb/s routed IP	3.1 M€/15y
2019/03/27	100 Gb/s routed IP	3.6 M€/15y
2019/10/17	2 × 100 Gb/s optical DWDM	< 3.6 M€/15y
2019/10/17	40 × 100 Gb/s optical DWDM	4.5 M€/15y
2019/10/17	60 × 100 Gb/s optical DWDM	5.2 M€/15y
2020/04/20	60 × 100 Gb/s optical DWDM	5.3 M€/15y

contract between EISCAT and NORDUnet. The advantages of the various WAN options regarding the deployment of the computing clusters and other e-infrastructure are given in Table 2. As the costs are given over a 15 year time, it can be seen that for approximately 100 k€/y (in WAN costs) all the computing can be moved from the RX sites to the central site. This has to be balanced with the expected costs (personnel, power supply, vendor service) of deploying all computing e-infrastructure to each of the two RX sites. Also, it can be seen in the above table that the price of the WAN connections varies over time. At the time of the first Stakeholder meeting in September of 2018, it was not feasible to propose a Tb/s WAN. As competitive market forces have intervened, the price for this technology has fallen dramatically and is likely to continue to do so.